

THE ROLE OF PROFESSIONAL REFLECTION IN THE PEDAGOGICAL ACTIVITY OF A PRIMARY SCHOOL TEACHER

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Abstract. *In this article, it is mentioned about the improvement of the functions of organization and management of the processes of formation of reflexive skills in elementary school teachers based on the analysis of information and prioritization of subject relations in cooperative activities.*

Keywords: *reflexive skills, subject, cooperative activities, teachers.*

In the world, education appears as the main factor that ensures the development of a person. In the international concept of education defined by UNESCO until 2030, "quality education stimulates creative thinking and knowledge, guarantees the acquisition of the basics of literacy and numeracy, as well as analytical, problem-solving, reasoning and other interpersonal and social skills at a high level" recorded. This defines the development of reflexive skills such as creative thinking, critical thinking, self-evaluation, understanding of historical reality, and analysis of one's own activities among students in the general secondary education system as an urgent task. The analysis of pedagogical experiences at the international level shows that the development of strategies for improving the processes of formation of reflexive skills in students and the design of mechanisms for its implementation are of great importance in ensuring the effectiveness of education.

The formation of reflexive skills in elementary school teachers, the teacher's more analytical thinking about himself, and the processes of independent assimilation of new concepts being learned by himself, that is, in the processes of independent thinking, when the teacher is not traditionally taught by the student, are realized in the general secondary educational institutions.

Encouraging primary school teachers to self-analysis, objective assessment of their concepts, activity and activity, i.e. reflexive activity, encouraging them to study history, the conditions of the period before the independence of our country and the historical way of life of our ancestors, encourage them to study, analyze and objectively evaluate situations creates. Therefore, in order to form reflexive skills in teachers, it is important to consider the following processes as directions of their reflexive activity:

1. Self-analysis and objective assessment: analysis of one's own concepts and perceptions; comparing their understanding, imagination and behavior with the understanding, imagination and behavior of their peers and siblings; objective assessment of one's own behavior; analyze how one is perceived by peers, comrades and other people; understanding and self-control with whom one interacts in the process of communication.

2. Comparison, analysis, objective evaluation and conclusion of the past (history) with the present: study of the relationship between the past and the present in relation to the studied concepts; their comparison, analysis and objective assessment; formation of objective ideas about

independence, its essence, importance and necessity; formation and development of reflexive activity skills.

In order to form a conscious discipline instead of forced obedience in the processes of formation and development of reflexive skills in elementary school teachers, it is necessary to take into account the following features specific to these processes: the teacher's activity with students is a unique integrative system; interdependence of students' inclinations, personal capabilities, initial concepts and personal interests;

Disproportion of effectiveness in the processes of formation and development of reflexive skills in teachers (paying special attention or not paying attention to the active student or group of students); the need to create a reflexive educational environment in educational institutions; that the processes of educational relations are of practical importance.

The process of forming reflexive skills in students is a complex pedagogical system that covers a wide range of features specific to the system. On the other hand, socio-psychological functions are performed by teachers in the process of effective performance of their functional tasks in this system.

Ensuring the effectiveness of the processes of forming reflexive skills in teachers in all aspects of planning, organization, motivation and control processes by leaders, specialists and teachers, effective information analysis, goal-motivation, foresight-planning, organizational-executive, control-diagnosis, regulation-coordination functions is intended to be implemented. The essence and importance of the implementation of these functions is expressed in the following processes: planning processes of formation and development of reflexive skills; ensuring the activity of teachers and forming their interest in learning; aligning the set goals and available opportunities with the interests and needs of students; to stimulate students' level of basic concepts, abilities, personal qualities, interests, as well as reflexive activities based on coordination, control, analysis and objective assessment.

The second pedagogical condition for the development of pedagogical reflection is the existence of a reflexive environment. Reflexive environment is a specific system of personal development conditions that open up the possibility of self-research of socio-psychological and professional resources and self-correction. The function of this type of environment is to create the basis for the need for reflection in the individual. A.A. Bizyaeva spoke about the "reflexive-innovative environment", where joint creativity is encouraged, conditions for selection are created, as a result of which a change occurs in the perception of oneself as a person and a professional. The goal of creating a reflexive environment is to prevent the pedagogue from moving away from the educational process and to develop professional reflexivity as a way of life (professional activity). Work with the thoughts and values of the pedagogue on the existential phenomenon, individual activity as the main directions of work in a reflexive environment; carrying out a psychologically safe (non-evaluation) diagnosis of professional qualities and using the obtained results to improve professional skills; the development of the creative uniqueness of the pedagogue is manifested.

The third pedagogical condition for the development of pedagogical reflection is the activation of intersubjective relations between the participants of reflexive activities. In the conditions of reflexive activity, the specific characteristics of the relationship in the pedagogical process require the participation of both the teacher and the learner as subjects of activity, in which their common activities take place synchronously, and each of them complements and enriches the

activities of each other while preserving the uniqueness of their actions. It is in such mutual transitions from subject-object relations to subject-subject relations that the mechanisms of professional reflection of the pedagogue are embodied.

The pedagogical process is organized and implemented by the teacher in order to create suitable conditions for the development of students. This means that all elements of reflection in the pedagogical process are related to reflections in the student's activity. This situation makes it necessary that the reflections on the future teacher's activity and the reflections of interaction are always proportional to the goal.

REFERENCES

1. Incheon Declaration/Education 2030: Towards inclusive and equitable quality education and lifelong learning for all (Word Education Forum, 19-22 may 2015, Incheon, Republic of Korea).
2. Метаева В.А. Рефлексия и её роль в преодолении профессиональных затруднений педагога: Дис. канд. пед. наук – Екатеринбург, 2016.- 207 с.
3. Хакимова Д.М. Ўқувчиларда рефлексив кўникмаларни шакллантиришнинг дидактик хусусиятлари. //Муғаллим ҳам узлуксиз билимлендириу. – Нукус, 2018.-№3. – Б. 21-22. (13.00.00 2018)
4. Семёнов И.Н. Развитие рефлексивно-критического мышления как компонента экзистенциально-ориентированного образования //Духовность и рефлексивность в становлении профессионала: Материалы межд.науч-практ. семинара: – М.: 1997.- С.27-32.